

SYNTHESIS OF α -ALKYL- γ -(4-METHOXY-3-CHLOROPHENYL)- BUTYRO LACTONES

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α -Alkyl- β -(4-methoxy-3-chlor. benzoyl)-propionic acids, prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction between *o*-chloroanisole and alkylsuccinic anhydrides, have been reduced and lactonised to furnish the corresponding α -alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

Extending the work of Rosenmund and Schapiro (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, 272, 313), Nargund *et al.* (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1944, 12A, Part V, 33) prepared α -alkyl- γ -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- and α -alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-tolyl)-butyro lactones. Buu-Hoi (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 1060) found 6-*tert.*-butyl-1-chloro-2-naphthol to be effective against tapeworms. A chlorophenyl group is of much therapeutic importance as can be judged by its presence in compounds like DDT, Paludrine, Chloroquine, Oxychloroquine, Camoquine and Atebrine. Alkyl group also plays a very important part in endowing a compound with important physiological properties; it also helps in lowering the toxicity of the compound. Resorcinol is toxic, but *n*-hexylresorcinol is an important internal (urinary) antiseptic and shows anthelmintic properties against a variety of intestinal worms (Leonard, *J. Urol.*, 1924, 12, 585; Lamson *et al.*, *Amer. J. Hyg.*, 1931, 13, 568). The importance of alkyl chain is also evident in 5-heptyl-2-thiohydantoin which shows antitubercle properties (Eroelich *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3099).

It was therefore of interest to prepare phenylbutyro lactones containing a chlorine, a methoxy and an alkyl group. α -Alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones have been prepared and described in the present work.

o-Chloroanisole was condensed with alkylsuccinic anhydrides in presence of aluminium chloride when α -alkyl- β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were obtained.

The anhydride of a mono-substituted succinic acid, when condensed by the Friedel-Crafts reaction, may give rise to two isomeric α - and β -substituted acids. Mehta, Bokil and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1943, 12A, Part III, 64) condensed anisole with alkylsuccinic anhydrides and obtained only one product, viz., α -alkyl- β -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid; Mehta, Trivedi, Bokil and Nargund (*ibid.*, 1944, 12, Part V, 35) similarly isolated only the α -acid in the case of condensation of alkylsuccinic anhydride with *o*-cresol methyl ethers.

The structure of the keto-acid has been assumed to be α -alkyl type as all keto-acids reacted with salicylaldehyde in the presence of dry hydrogen chloride in methyl

alcoholic solution to furnish crimson-red pyrrillium derivatives, thus indicating the presence of COCH_3 grouping (Decker and Fallenberg, *Annalen*, 1907, 366, 302; Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1085; Desai and Wali, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 135):

The keto-acids, obtained by the condensation of *o*-chloroanisole with alkylsuccinic anhydrides, were oxidised by hot dilute alkaline potassium permanganate when an acid, m.p. 215° , was obtained. It was identified (mixed m.p.) as 4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoic acid (Schall and Dralle, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2529). Thus, the constitution of the keto-acids is assumed as α -alkyl- β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids.

Ethyl esters of these keto acids were reduced by aluminium isopropoxide, and lactonisation of the resulting hydroxy-acids furnished α -alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

EXPERIMENTAL

n-Propyl-, *n*-butyl- and *n*-hexyl-succinic acids were prepared by the condensation of *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-hexyl halides with malonic ester and ethyl chloroacetate and subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation. Methyl-, ethyl- and *n*-amyl-succinic acids were prepared by the condensation of ethyl α -halo-propionate, butyrate and -heptylate with ethyl malonate and subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation.

α -Alkyl- β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic Acids.—Alkylsuccinic anhydride (0.1M) was condensed in cold with *o*-chloroanisole (0.1M) by the Friedel-Crafts reaction, using a mixture of tetrachloro-ethane (80 c.c.) and nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) as solvent. After the addition of aluminium chloride (0.2M), the reaction mixture was kept for 24 hours in a cold water-bath. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and HCl. The solvent mixture was removed by steam distillation and the solid product obtained on cooling was filtered. The keto-acids were purified through their sodium salts.

α -Alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyro Lactones.—Ethyl α -alkyl- β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionate (0.03M) was refluxed with aluminium isopropoxide (0.03M) in dry isopropyl alcohol (30 c.c.) till the distillate was free of acetone (Roger Adams, "Org. Reactions", Vol. II, p. 196). After removal of isopropyl alcohol, HCl (dil.) was added and the organic layer separating was refluxed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (30 c.c., 20% in 15 c.c. EtOH). After distilling off alcohol, the residue was diluted with water and the neutral impurities were removed with ether. The solution was then acidified with 25% H_2SO_4 (dil.) and more of the acid was added so as to bring the concentration of the acid to about 15%. It was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours. The product obtained on cooling was kept over a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate for 24 hours so as to remove the acidic impurities from the lactone. If the product obtained was a liquid, it was extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), followed with water. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure. In case of solids, the product was dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent. The lactones were obtained in 50 to 60% yield.

The compounds are tabulated in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

PA denotes β -(4-methoxy-3-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid.

D.N.P. ,, dinitrophenylhydrazone.

No.	Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	Properties.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	α -Methyl-PA	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4Cl$	Needles from hot water, m.p. 140° .	14.0 (253.2)	13.8 (256.5)
2	Ethyl ester of (1)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $214-17^\circ/8$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.524.	12.7	12.4
3	Semicarbazone of (1)	$C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_3Cl$	Needles from dil. alcohol, m.p. 165° .	11.5 (315.3)	11.3 (313.5)
4	α -Ethyl-PA	$C_{13}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Do from benzene, m.p. 129° .	13.3 (269)	13.1 (270.5)
5	Ethyl ester of (4)	$C_{15}H_{19}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $220-25^\circ/6$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.53.	12.2	11.9
6	Oxime of (4)	$C_{13}H_{16}O_4NCl$	Needles from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 139° .	12.7	12.4
7	α -n-Propyl-PA	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	Needles from benzene-petrol, m.p. 102° .	12.6 (285.9)	12.5 (284.5)
8	Ethyl ester (7)	$C_{16}H_{21}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $221-25^\circ/8$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.525.	11.6	11.4
9	Oxime of (7)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_4NCl$	Needles from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 140° .	12.1	11.9
10	α -n-Butyl-PA	$C_{15}H_{19}O_4Cl$	Do from hot water, m.p. 100°	12.1 (300.4)	11.9 (288.5)
11	Ethyl ester of (10)	$C_{17}H_{23}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $226-30^\circ/8$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.516.	11.1	10.9
12	2:4-D.N.P. of (10)	$C_{21}H_{25}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from EtOH, m.p. 213° .	7.6	7.4
13	α -n-Amyl-PA	$C_{16}H_{21}O_4Cl$	Needles from benzene-petrol, m.p. 98° .	11.5 (310.3)	11.3 (312.5)
14	Ethyl ester of (13)	$C_{18}H_{25}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $244-47^\circ/5$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.458.	10.6	10.4
15	2:4-D.N.P. of (13)	$C_{22}H_{26}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from EtOH, m.p. 208°	7.3	7.2
16	α -n-Hexyl-PA	$C_{17}H_{23}O_4Cl$	Needles from benzene, m.p. 129° .	11.1 (325.0)	10.9 (326.5)
17	Ethyl ester of (16)	$C_{19}H_{27}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $253-57^\circ/8$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.456.	10.2	10.0
18	2:4-D.N.P. of (16)	$C_{23}H_{27}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from EtOH, m.p. 182° .	7.2	7.0

N.B. Figures in parentheses in last two columns refer to equiv. weights.

TABLE II

No.	Alkyl- γ -(4-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-butyrolactones.	Formula.	Properties.	% Chlorine.		Equiv.-wt.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	α -Methyl-	$C_{12}H_{13}O_3Cl$	Liquid, b.p. $205-10^{\circ}/8$ mm. n_D^{20} , 1.534.	14.9	14.7	237.2	240.5
2	α -Ethyl-	$C_{13}H_{15}O_3Cl$	Plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 85° .	14.2	13.9	252.7	254.5
3	α - <i>n</i> -Propyl-	$C_{14}H_{17}O_3Cl$	Needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 88° .	13.4	13.2	271.0	268.5
4	α - <i>n</i> -Butyl-	$C_{15}H_{19}O_3Cl$	Plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 89° .	12.7	12.6	290.0	281.5
5	α - <i>n</i> -Amyl-	$C_{16}H_{21}O_3Cl$	Plates from alcohol, m.p. 92° .	12.2	12.0	294.8	296.5
6	α - <i>n</i> -Hexyl-	$C_{17}H_{23}O_3Cl$	Do, m.p. 89° .	11.7	11.4	309.0	310.5

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